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Report on available biomarkers of effect of utility in human epidemiological studies for the 1st set of prioritised substances

Deliverable Report

D 14.3

WP14 - Biomarkers of Effect

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2 Glossary

AD	Additional Deliverable
AOP	Adverse Outcome Pathways
AWP	Annual Work Plan
BDNF	Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor
D	Deliverable
EBCs	European Birth Cohorts
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU	European Human Biomonitoring Initiative
MB	Management Board
UGR	University of Granada
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

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3 Abstract/Summary

Work Package 14 partners have carried out a wide literature survey on existing biomarkers of effects for the first set of prioritised substances published in Deliverable D14.2. The aim of Task 14.3 was to identify available effect biomarkers of utility in human epidemiological studies.

Selection of these biomarkers has been based on: the type of human health effects prioritised for each chemical substance, the quality of the assay, its usefulness for large population studies, the added value it provides, and the degree of validation (accuracy, sensitivity, sensibility, and reproducibility across different studies).

During the discussion at the 2018 Granada Workshop, referenced in Additional Deliverable AD14.2, we focused on the selection of effect biomarkers of utility for HBM studies to be applied in HBM4EU-aligned research. In addition, existing and consolidated European human epidemiological studies, as well as European Birth Cohorts (EBCs) participating in HBM4EU, have been also identified as a result of the interaction between Work Package 14 and Work Package 13 and the corresponding researcher contacts provided. The natural continuation of Work Package 14 work will lead to the implementation of selected traditional and novel effect biomarkers in HBM4EU-aligned studies and in European cohorts, providing a unique opportunity for their initial implementation following the proposed “strategy”, which connects and integrates all Work Package 14 tasks with HBM4EU-aligned studies.

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4 Introduction

One of the objectives of Work Package 14 (“Effect biomarkers”) was to carry out a wide literature survey on existing biomarkers of effects for the first set of prioritised substances:

- Bisphenols;
- Phthalates;
- Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs);
- Perfluorinated compounds (PFAS, PFOAs);
- Organophosphate (OPFRs) and Brominated (BFRs) Flame retardants; and
- Cadmium (Cd).

For this purpose a criteria of prioritisation was defined including both qualitative and quantitative criteria, in order to rank the biomarkers of effect found. Priority was given to:

- i) Biomarkers implemented in epidemiologic studies over those that had not been validated in human populations;
- ii) Biomarkers of effect related to mechanisms of action (MOA) and/or Key Events (KE) in Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs);
- iii) The cost-benefit ratio in relation to the efficacy/innovative potential of the biomarker under study;
- iv) Biomarkers of effect applied in both clinical and epidemiological settings, as well as those applied in human matrices not invasively; and
- v) Specificity, sensitivity, and reliability of the biological changes in relation to the chemical exposure and interpretation of the biological change.

Additionally, the selected effect biomarkers were categorised according to their biological level of complexity:

- i) Omics;
- ii) Biochemical / physiological biomarkers;
- iii) In vitro/ex vivo cell-based biomarkers; and
- iv) Anthropometric biomarkers.

These criteria are described in [Deliverable D14.1](#).

Deliverable D14.2 reports the results of the literature searches conducted for the first set of prioritised substances. It has provided a huge amount of different effect biomarkers that have been implemented with more or less success in human epidemiological studies. The methodological details of the comprehensive revision, including search terms, databases and procedures are extensively described in D14.2.

Some of them have highlighted the role of reproductive, thyroid and adrenal hormones, as well as metabolic parameters such as serum lipids, glucose and insulin as relevant effect biomarkers associated with most chemical families studied. These biomarkers are commonly and routinely analysed in different laboratories and their cost is very affordable. Moreover, there are no big concerns about the validity and reliability of these measurements. In addition, these traditional and more studied effect biomarkers are usually included in other human monitoring-health initiatives.

Work Package 14 presented a proposal for measuring a basic list of those effect biomarkers to the management board celebrated in Berlin, May 2018. Some concerns emerged as to whether this minimum list of traditional effect biomarkers should be implemented or not in HBM4EU aligned

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studies, without a more careful and specific selection according to the experimental data available for each of the chemical families, and the window of development assessed (children, adolescents or adults).

As it was stated in the Annual Work Plan (AWP), the selection of the effect biomarkers of utility in human epidemiological studies should be based on the type of human health effects that will be prioritised for each chemical substance, the quality of the assay, its usefulness for large population studies, the added value that they provided, as well as the degree of validation (accuracy, sensitivity, sensibility, and reproducibility across different studies).

In addition, WP14 is focusing on effect biomarkers with three main big aims throughout the whole HBM4EU project:

- a) To summarise the most relevant effect biomarkers, including those that have been successfully employed in environmental epidemiologic settings;
- b) To identify the gaps in knowledge regarding effect biomarkers in human biomonitoring;
- c) To research and implement promising novel effect biomarkers that can provide an added value to human biomonitoring studies; and
- d) To increase the knowledge concerning alterations in biological pathways that precede disease diagnosis, the so-called Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs).

The HBM4EU initiative aims to fill the existing gap in European countries regarding a coordinated biomonitoring assessment of environmental contaminants in human populations. In doing so, and taking into account several aspects, it has been decided that childhood, adolescence and adulthood will be the prioritised population groups of study for the aligned studies that will be the focus of HBM4EU. Although this decision will facilitate the consecution of the main HBM4EU objectives, it cannot be forgotten that pregnancy is still considered as the most vulnerable and critical window of exposure to environmental pollutants, endocrine disruptors and other environmental stressors.

4.1 Identification of European human epidemiological studies participating in HBM4EU

4.1.1 Data gathering

Existing and consolidated European human epidemiological studies, as well as European Birth Cohorts (EBCs) represent a unique opportunity to complement HBM4EU objectives, especially when it comes to new development regarding applying novel or less studied effect biomarkers that can be of interest for improving our understanding of pregnancy, infancy and childhood outcomes in response to environmental exposures.

Work Package 14 literature searched has also provided information about past and currently European human epidemiological studies. In addition, several birth cohort studies assessing children's health have been initiated during the past two decades in Europe. Information was found in the retrieved papers and confirmed visiting the websites of relevant projects related to European cohorts [for example (www.enrieco.org) (<http://www.birthcohorts.net>) and (<http://www.chicosproject.eu/cohorts/>)] (Vrijheid et al. 2012; Bousquet et al. 2013; Piler et al. 2017), regarding number of participants, the duration, the follow-up frequency, the collection of biological materials, investigated biomarkers, and other environmental factors.

Additionally, Vicente Mustieles (University of Granada) conducted a short stay of 10 ten days at ISGLOBAL (Barcelona, Spain), in order to discuss future work through interactions between the HBM4EU project and established European birth cohorts. Information contained from the draft of

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Deliverable D1.6 “Second Ethics Report” was also searched for, in order to integrate those birth cohorts or biobanks participating in HBM4EU that could also be of interest for the future implementation of novel effect biomarkers. Thus, established European birth cohorts focused on environmental health research coordinated by teams participating in HBM4EU were selected.

The following European birth cohort studies were identified based on the articles read, websites, previous knowledge, word of mouth, and using data from Deliverable D1.6 “Second Ethics Report”:

European birth cohorts	HBM4EU partners involved
INMA –Sabadell (Spain) Mother-Child cohort	ISGLOBAL Martine Vrijheid martine.vrijheid@isglobal.org
INMA-Granada (Spain) Mother-child cohort Peripubertal boys	UGR Mariana F. Fernández marieta@ugr.es
EDEN (France) Mother-Child cohort	INSERM Barbara Heude barbara.heude@inserm.fr
FLEHS I, II and III (Belgium) Birth, Adolescent and Adult cohorts FLEHS IV (Belgium) Adolescent cohort (Belgium)	VITO Vera Nelen (Flemish Monitoring Commission) vera.nelen@pih.provant.be Greet Schoeters greet.schoeters@vito.be
CELSPAC (Czech Republic) Mother-child cohort	MU Jana Klánová klanova@recetox.muni.cz
FETOTOX (Denmark) Mother-child cohort	AU Eva Cecilie Bonefeld-Jorgensen ebj@ph.au.dk
Greenlandic Birth cohort (Greenland) Mother-child cohort	AU Eva Cecilie Bonefeld-Jorgensen ebj@ph.au.dk
PELAGIE (France) Mother-child cohort	INSERM Cécile Chevrier cecile.chevrier@inserm.fr
SEPAGES (France) Mother-child cohort	INSERM Rémy Slama remy.slama@inserm.fr
3XG Birth Cohort (Belgium) Mother-child cohort	VITO Greet Schoeters greet.schoeters@vito.be
ELFE (France) Mother-Child cohort	INSERM Marie-Aline Charles marie-aline.charles@inserm.fr

INMA (Environment and Childhood); **CELSPAC** (Central European Longitudinal Study of Pregnancy and Childhood); **EDEN** (Study on the pre- and early postnatal determinants of child health and development); **FETOTOX** (study combining data from two Danish birth cohorts with two international birth cohorts); **FLESH** (Flemish Environment and Health Study); **ELFE** (French Longitudinal Study of Children); **PELAGIE** (a French birth cohort comprising 3,421 pregnant women recruited between 2002 and 2006).

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In addition, some effect biomarkers were identified based from epidemiological studies on the articles read based on the first set of prioritised chemical families and the health outcome. A selection of effect biomarkers was also proposed for their implementation in the HBM4EU aligned studies (see Table 1 and Table 2, at the end of this document).

During the Granada Workshop 2018 (AD14.2), the process of selection of effect biomarkers of utility for HBM studies and HBM4EU aligned studies was discussed in detail as a result of the interaction between WP13 and WP14. All workshops' participants finally agreed that the best way to select biomarkers of effect for HBM and HBM4EU was to take into account the experimental knowledge available, ideally using the Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) framework. A process with different steps was proposed to favour WP13-WP14 interaction: to organise mixed groups with partners from both WP13 and WP14 for each chemical family in order to select the best epidemiologic effect biomarkers that can better assess what is known at an experimental level, trying to follow a similar scheme (see below). The decisions are based on each chemical group, the adverse outcomes of highest interest, and the critical window of exposure.

The joint WP13 and WP14 activities are now taking place (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/upload-work-package/get/file/WP13amp14-joint-activities-LEADERS-and-PARTNERS.docx>) and its results will be gradually reported and updated in future deliverables (e.g. AD14.3, M24).

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4.2 A gradual approach for the implementation of traditional and novel effect biomarkers in HBM4EU

The literature searches on effect biomarkers (D14.2) have made possible the identification of gaps in knowledge regarding effect biomarkers. The following slide shows how both, pilot studies and the implantation of biomarker of effects in different established cohorts, can help to understand the biological consequences of relevant environmental exposures.

As an example, one important gap in knowledge is the selection of biochemical effect biomarkers for neurodevelopmental health, which could provide useful complementary information in addition to the frequently used neuropsychological questionnaires (see D14.2). One of the candidate effect biomarkers to be explored in order to fill this data gap is the measurement of the brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) in children biological samples. Task 14.3 partner (UGR) will measure BDNF levels in peripubertal boys from the INMA-Granada cohort, to investigate if BDNF urinary levels are related to behaviour or cognitive, in addition to the information gathered in several neuropsychological tests. In this way, if BDNF or any other novel effect biomarkers are shown to be useful, they could be proposed for their implementation in HBM4EU aligned studies.

Overall, this “strategy” can provide a practical way of connecting all the tasks that are being developed within WP14 (literature searches on effect biomarkers, research on novel effect biomarkers to cover gaps in knowledge), with the objective of providing an added value to HBM in general, and to HBM4EU in particular.

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5 Conclusions and future actions

Different European cohorts participating in HBM4EU have been identified in this deliverable, and the corresponding researcher's email contacts provided. The natural continuation of WP14 work (Deliverables D14.2 and D14.4) may and should lead to the implementation of novel effect biomarkers in epidemiologic settings, and these European cohorts provide a unique opportunity for their initial implementation, following the proposed "strategy", which connects and integrates all WP14 tasks with HBM4EU aligned studies.

Additionally, it will be also be of interest to identify and consider the consultation with investigators involved in Human Biomonitoring Initiatives around the world, such as the U.S. ECHO initiative.

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7 Selection of effect biomarkers of utility in human epidemiological studies

Table 1: Selection of effect biomarkers of utility in human epidemiological studies

Chemical Family	Health Endpoint						
	Allergy-Immune System	Reproductive	Endocrine	Cardio-Metabolic-Obesity	Neurodevelopment	Cancer	Others
Bisphenols	Immunoglobulin E (IgE)	<p>Reproductive Hormones: Luteinizing hormone (LH), Follicle Stimulating Hormone (FSH), Sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG), Total testosterone (TT), Estradiol (E2).</p> <p>Semen quality</p>	<p>Thyroid Hormones: Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH), Triiodothyronine (T₃), Thyroxine (T₄),</p>	<p>Glucose Metabolism: Fasting blood glucose (FBG); Fasting insulin levels; Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c); Homeostatic model assessment (HOMA); HOMA-IR= (Fasting blood glucose (FBG) x Insulin) / 450).</p> <p>Serum Lipids: Low density lipoprotein (LDL), high density lipoprotein (HDL), total cholesterol (TC) and triglycerides (TG)</p> <p>Liver Enzymes: Alanine transaminase (ALT), Aspartate transaminase (AST), Alkaline phosphatase (ALP), Gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT), Serum bilirubin.</p> <p>Blood pressure Chronic inflammation: C reactive protein (CRP) IL-6, TNF-α).</p>	<p>Neuropsychological test</p> <p>CBCL: Child Behavior Check-List (6-18 years). SDQ: Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire BASC-2: Behavior Assessment System for Children BRIEF-P: Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function-Preschool WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children.</p>	<p>DNA damage: 8-oxo-7,8-dihydro-2'-deoxyguanosine (8-oxodGuo or 8-OHdG) and 8-isoprostane.</p>	<p>Anthropometric: Birth Weight, Birth Length, Head Circumference; Body Max Index (BMI), Skinfold Thickness, Anogenital Distance (AGD).</p> <p>Renal Function: Albuminuria Glomerular Filtration Rate (GFR)</p>

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Chemical Family	Health Endpoint						
	Allergy-Immune System	Reproductive	Endocrine	Cardio-Metabolic-Obesity	Neurodevelopment	Cancer	Others
Phthalates	Immunoglobulin E (IgE)	Reproductive Hormones: Luteinizing hormone (LH), Follicle Stimulating Hormone (FSH), Sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG), Total testosterone (TT), Estradiol (E2). Semen quality	Thyroid hormones levels: Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH), Triiodothyronine (T ₃), Thyroxine (T ₄),	Glucose metabolism Fasting blood glucose (FBG); Fasting insulin levels; Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c); Homeostatic model assessment (HOMA); HOMA-IR= (Fasting blood glucose (FBG) x Insulin) / 450). Serum Lipids: Low density lipoprotein (LDL), high density lipoprotein (HDL), total cholesterol (TC) and triglycerides (TG) Adipokines: Adiponectin, Leptin Blood pressure	Neurobehavioral tests: CBCL: Child Behaviour Checklist SDQ: Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire VMWM: Virtual Morris Water Maze Questionnaires: Changes in sex-typical play behaviors	DNA damage: 8-oxo-7,8-dihydro-2'-deoxyguanosine (8-oxodGuo or 8-OHdG) and 8-isoprostane	Anthropometric parameters (BMI, waist circumference). Weight changes, hip and femur bone density. Anthropometrics at birth Birth Weight, Birth Length, Head Circumference; Body Max Index (BMI), Skinfold Thickness, Anogenital Distance (AGD).
Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs)	DNA damage and genotoxicity: Commet Assay CBMN assay (Lymphocyte Cytokinesis-Block Micronucleous Assay). DNA damage 8-oxo-deoxyguanosine formation (8-OHdG)						
Perfluorinated compounds	CC16: Club cell secretory protein Serum IgE. Absolute eosinophil counts (AEC), eosinophilic	Reproductive Hormones: LH, FSH, Estradiol, Testosterone, SHBG, Progesterone, Dihydroepiandroster	Thyroid Hormones: FT3, FT4, TSH, TT3, TT4,	Glucose metabolism Fasting blood glucose (FBG); Fasting insulin levels; Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c); Homeostatic model assessment (HOMA);	Cognition or IQ Tests.	Cell-based estrogenic assay: Combined xenoestrogenic	Renal Function: Uric acid levels. Anthropometric: Fetal growth /size at birth.

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Chemical Family	Health Endpoint						
	Allergy-Immune System	Reproductive	Endocrine	Cardio-Metabolic-Obesity	Neurodevelopment	Cancer	Others
(PFAs, PFOAs)	cationic protein (ECP) concentrations. Basophils count. Lymphocytes subpopulations: B cells, CD4-positive T helper cells. Anti-keratin IgG, anti-actin IgG.	one (DHEA).		<p>HOMA-IR= (Fasting blood glucose (FBG) x Insulin) / 450).</p> <p>Serum Lipids: Low density lipoprotein (LDL), high density lipoprotein (HDL), total cholesterol (TC) and triglycerides (TG)</p> <p>Liver Function: ALT, GGT, Total bilirubin, GOT, GPT.</p> <p>Adipokines: Adiponectin</p> <p>Others: Blood pressure.</p>		effect (breast cancer).	BMI. Waist-to-height ratio. Bone density.
Brominated Flame Retardants (BFRs)		Reproductive Hormones: LH, FSH, Testosterone (T), estradiol(E2), SHBG, Growth Hormone (GH),	Thyroid Hormones: Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH), Triiodothyronine (T ₃), Thyroxine (T ₄),	<p>Glucose metabolism Fasting blood glucose (FBG); Fasting insulin levels; Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c); Homeostatic model assessment (HOMA); HOMA-IR= (Fasting blood glucose (FBG) x Insulin) / 450).</p> <p>Serum Lipids: Low density lipoprotein (LDL), high density lipoprotein (HDL), total</p>			<p>Anthropometric: BMI: Body fat;</p> <p>Inflammation: CRP (C-reactive protein)</p>

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Chemical Family	Health Endpoint						
	Allergy-Immune System	Reproductive	Endocrine	Cardio-Metabolic-Obesity	Neurodevelopment	Cancer	Others
				cholesterol (TC) and triglycerides (TG) Liver Function: ALT, GGT, Total bilirubin, GOT, GPT. Adipokines: Leptin			
Organophos. Flame Retardants (OPFRs)		Reproductive hormones: Luteinizing hormone (LH), Follicle Stimulating Hormone (FSH), Sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG), Total testosterone (TT), Estradiol (E2).	Thyroid hormones fT4, TT4, TT3, TSH. Semen quality	Cardiovascular Function: SM, Cer, Sph, S1P protein	Social Behavior (Skills Improvement Rating scale). WISC-IV. Standard Progressive matrices test.	DNA damage: 8-OHdG	
Cadmium (Cd)							Renal Function: Marker of tubular damage: B2MG: Urinary Beta-2 microglobulin NAG: N-acetyl- β -D glucosaminidase Serum creatinine, urinary albumin Oxidative stress: 8-OHdG, 8-isoprostane

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8 List of proposal of effect biomarkers to be implemented in the HBM4EU aligned studies

Table 2: Selection of possible effect biomarkers to be implemented in the HBM4EU aligned studies provided by WP8 (based on window of exposure - children, adolescents or adults-, chemical family, and adverse outcome of highest concern)

Cohort Age Chemicals	Health Endpoint	Children (6-11 y) 2700-3000 participants	Adolescents (12-19 y) 2700-3000 participants	Adults (20-40 y) 2700-3000 participants
Phthalates, DINCH	Neurodevelopment	<p>Neurobehavioral Tests: CBCL(6-18): Child Behavior Checklist WISC-IV (6-16y) Wechler Intelligence Scale for Children</p> <p>Neurodevelopment Brain Derived Neurotrophic Factor (BDNF), GDNF or Sp4</p>		Not measured in adults
	Reproductive	<p>Reproductive Hormones (Serum): Luteinizing hormone (LH), Follicle Stimulating Hormone (FSH), Sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG), Total testosterone (TT), Estradiol (E2). Serum Kisspeptin (KiSS)</p> <p>Gene expression of nuclear receptors in blood (monocytes, lymphocytes): Estrogen receptors (ER) α and β, Androgen receptor (AR), Arylhydrocarbon Receptor (AhR), Pregnane X receptor (PXR), Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor (PPAR) γ</p>		
	Endocrine	<p>Thyroid hormones levels (Serum): Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH), Triiodothyronine (T₃), Thyroxine (T₄)</p>		
	Metabolic-Obesity	<p>Glucose metabolism (Serum): Fasting blood glucose (FBG); Fasting insulin levels; Glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c); Homeostatic model assessment (HOMA); HOMA-IR= (Fasting blood glucose (FBG) x Insulin) / 450).</p> <p>Serum Lipids: Low density lipoprotein (LDL), high density lipoprotein (HDL), total cholesterol (TC) and triglycerides (TG)</p> <p>Adipokines (Serum): Adiponectin, Leptin</p> <p>Anthropometrics: BMI z-score; Body fat mass; Blood pressure</p>		
	Allergy/Immune	Serum Immunoglobulin E (IgE)		

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Cohort Age	Health Endpoint	Children (6-11 y)	Adolescents (12-19 y)	Adults (20-40 y)
Chemicals				
Flame retardants	Neurodevelopment	WISC-IV (6-16y) Neurodevelopment Brain Derived Neurotrophic Factor (BDNF), GDNF or Sp4	<i>Not measured in adolescents</i>	<i>Not measured in adults</i>
	Reproductive	Reproductive hormones (Serum): LH, FSH, SHBG, TT, E2		
	Endocrine	Thyroid Hormones (Serum): TSH, T ₃ , T ₄		
	Metabolic-Obesity	Glucose metabolism (Serum): FBG, Fasting insulin levels; HbA1, HOMA-IR Serum Lipids: LDL, HDL, TC, TG Adipokines (Serum): Adiponectin, Leptin Inflammation (Serum): CRP (C-reactive protein) Anthropometrics: BMI z-score; Body fat mass		
	Allergy/Immune	Serum IgE		

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Cohort Age	Health Endpoint	Children (6-11 y)	Adolescents (12-19 y)	Adults (20-40 y)
Chemicals	Neurodevelopment	<i>Not measured in children</i>	<u>Neurodevelopment Test:</u> WISC-IV (6-16y) <u>Neurodevelopment</u> Brain Derived Neurotrophic Factor (BDNF), GDNF or Sp4	<i>Not measured in adults</i>
	Reproductive		<u>Reproductive Hormones:</u> LH, FSH, E2, TT, SHBG	
	Endocrine		<u>Thyroid Hormones:</u> TSH, T3,T4	
	Metabolic-Obesity		<u>Glucose metabolism</u> FBG, Fasting insulin levels; HbA1, HOMA-IR <u>Serum Lipids:</u> LDL, HDL, TC, TG <u>Liver Enzymes:</u> Alanine transaminase (ALT), Aspartate transaminase (AST), Alkaline phosphatase (ALP), Gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT), Serum bilirubin. <u>Adipokines:</u> Adiponectin, leptin <u>Others:</u> BMI z-scores; Body fat; Blood pressure. <u>Gene expression of nuclear receptors in blood (monocytes or lymphocytes or whole blood):</u> PPAR α , γ , δ , Genes of cholesterol metabolism: NR1H2 (LXRB), NR1H3 (LXRA), NCEH1, ABCG1 and NPC1	

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	Allergy-Immune		<p>Serum IgE, Absolute eosinophil counts (AEC), eosinophilic cationic protein (ECP). Basophils count.</p> <p>Lymphocytes subpopulation (B cells, CD4-positive T helper cells.</p> <p>Serum antibody concentrations against common infectious.</p>	
Cohort Age	Health Endpoint	Children (6-11 y)	Adolescents (12-19 y)	Adults (20-40 y)
Chemicals				
Bisphenols	Reproductive	<i>Not measured in children</i>	<i>Not measured in adults</i>	<p>Reproductive Hormones (Serum): LH, FSH, E2, TT, SHBG KISS</p> <p>Semen quality</p> <p>Gene expression of nuclear receptors in blood (monocytes or lymphocytes): ERα and β, AR, ESRRα, ESRRβ</p>
	Endocrine			<p>Thyroid Hormones: TSH, T3, T4</p>
	Obesity-Metabolic-Cardiovascular			<p>Glucose Metabolism: FBG, Fasting insulin levels; HbA1, HOMA-IR</p> <p>Serum Lipids: LDL, HDL, TC, TG</p> <p>Liver Enzymes: ALT, AST, ALP, GGT, Serum bilirubin.</p> <p>Anthropometrics: BMI z-scores; Body fat; Blood pressure</p> <p>Chronic inflammation: C reactive protein (CRP) IL-6, TNF-α).</p>

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	Allergy/Immune			Serum IgE
	Hormone-dependent cancers			Urinary hydroxyestrogens: 2-metoxysterone 2-metoxiestradiol 4-metoxysterone 4-metoxiestradiol 16-alpha-hydroxyestosterone
Cohort Age Chemicals	Health Endpoint	Children (6-11 y)	Adolescents (12-19 y)	Adults (20-40 y)
PAHs	Cancer (Blood or Urine samples)	Not measured in children	Not measured in adolescents	DNA damage Urinary 8-oxo-deoxyguanosine concentrations (8-OHdG) DNA damage and genotoxicity (serum): Commet Assay or CBMN assay (Lymphocyte Cytokinesis-Block Micronucleous Assay).
	Respiratory health (Blood or Urine sample)			Pulmonary function: CC16: Club cell secretory protein (Serum and/or urine)
Cohort Age Chemicals	Health Endpoint	Children (6-11 y)	Adolescents (12-19 y)	Adults (20-40 y)
Cadmium	Renal Function	Not measured in children	Not measured in adolescents	Markers of tubular damage: Urinary Beta-2 microglobulin (B2MG) concentrations Urinary N-acetyl-β-D glucosaminidase (NAG) concentrations Markers of glomerular function: Urinary albumin concentrations Novel markers: Urinary levels

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				of Kidney Injury Molecule (KIM-1) and Cystatin C.
	Oxidative Stress			Urinary levels of 8-OHdG, 8-isoprostane